

A set of 16 locally used TVs and MVs were crossed with V20 A, which was used as the female parent. Five spikelets were selected from each plant before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two or three anthers from each spikelet were placed together on a glass slide and squashed in 1% iodine solution. Slides were screened for sterile/fertile pollen. Estimates were based on five panicles from bagged hybrid plants.

Maintainers and restorers for V20 A were identified based on pollen and spikelet fertility (see table). Maintainers

were more frequent than restorers. Himdhan, R575, Kaladhan, CH1039, IR18482-Plp3-2-5-2, HPU2202, Debal, HPU5101, and CH988 had 100% pollen sterility and were identified as effective maintainers for V20 A.

Pollen fertility did not show any correlation ($r = 0.24$) with spikelet fertility. Therefore, spikelet fertility was used to identify restorers. Effective restorers have spikelet fertility of 80% and above.

K39, Himalaya 741, HPU799, HPU2216, IR9129-263-3-3-2-3-2, and

HPU5039-Plp13-4-4-6-3B were classified as partial restorers, which means spikelet fertility is less than 80% but 10% or more.

These findings indicate that effective maintainers are common among rice cultivars adapted to HP's conditions. New CMS lines possessing WA cytoplasm and from different genetic backgrounds can be developed by recurrent backcrossing procedure. Effective restorers for WA cytoplasm still need to be identified among locally adapted rice cultivars to develop heterotic rice hybrids. ■

Maintainers and restorers for four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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Screening elite breeding lines for effective and genetically diverse maintainers and restorers for different CMS lines is important in developing new CMS lines and productive hybrids.

Short-, medium-, and long-duration rice cultivars were used as pollen parents for crossing with WA-type CMS lines PMS-3 A, PMS-10 A, IR62829 A, and V20 A. The F_1 hybrids were evaluated for spikelet fertility during the 1992 wet season (WS).

Rice cultivars with 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as effective restorers, those with 1-79% as partial restorers, and those with less than 1% as effective maintainers.

All the test cultivars except IET10485, IET11831, IET12395, and RR8585 were identified as effective maintainers (see table). IET11831 proved to be an effective restorer for PMS-3 A and PMS-10 A, and a partial restorer for IR62829 A. IET10749 restored the fertility of PMS-10 A but maintained the sterility of PMS-3 A and IR62829 A. IET10485 and IET12395, however, partially restored the fertility of IR62829 A and PMS-3 A, respectively. Only RR8585 restored the fertility of all four CMS lines. ■

Maintainers and restorers for PMS-3 A, PMS-10 A, IR62829 A, and V20 A.^a RARS, R. S. Pura, India, 1992 WS.

Variety	CMS lines			
	PMS-3 A	PMS-10 A	IR62829 A	V20 A
RR8585	R	R	R	R
IET10485	M	-	PR	-
IET10749	M	R	M	-
IET11074	M	M	M	-
IET11831	R	R	PR	-
IET12395	PR	-	M	-
IET12403	-	M	-	R
IET13152	-	M	-	M
Kasturi	M	M	-	M
R. Basmati	M	M	M	M
Giza 14 (japonica)	M	M	M	-

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, M = maintainer.

Identifying maintainers and restorers of cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines for hybrid rice breeding

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We used 25 varieties as male parents to make 132 crosses with CMS lines V20 A, IR46830 A, IR54752 A, ES18 A, Madhu A, Pragathi A, Pushpa A, and Mangla A (Table 1) to identify maintainers and restorers with varying tolerance for agroclimatic stress and resistance to biotic stress.

Pollen from each CMS line was tested with 1% iodine solution before crossing and found to have a high degree of

sterility. The pollen parents and F_1 s were transplanted together to determine maintainers and restorers. Panicles were bagged before emergence to avoid outcrossing.

Spikelet fertility of F_1 s and parents (10 plants each) was recorded at the Crop Research Station (CRS), Masodha, Faizabad, during 1987-90 wet seasons

Table 1. CMS lines used in the study.

CMS line	Origin	Source of cytoplasm
V20 A	China	Wild abortive
IR46830 A	IRRI	Wild abortive
IR54752 A	IRRI	Wild abortive
ES18 A	India	MS 577
Madhu A	India	MS 577
Pragathi A	India	MS 577
Pushpa A	India	MS 577
Mangla A	India	MS 577

Table 2. Height, duration, and fertility of F₁s test crops involving 8 CMS lines.* CRS, Masodha, Faizabad, UP, India, 1987-90 WS.

Variety	Height	Duration	1987-88		1988-89		1989-90			
			V20 A	IR46830 A	IR54752 A	ES18 A	Madhu A	Pragathi A	Pushpa A	Mangla A
Narendra 1	Dwarf	Early	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Narendra 2	Dwarf	Early	PR	PR	PR	—	PR	PM	—	PM
Narendra 80	Tall	Early	PR	PM	PR	—	PM	—	PM	PM
Narendra 1.18	Dwarf	Early	R	PR	R	PR	PR	—	PM	PM
IR8	Dwarf	Medium	PM	—	PR	PM	PM	—	PM	—
IR24	Dwarf	Medium	R	R	PR	PM	PM	—	PM	—
Saket 1	Tall	Early	PR	PR	R	—	PM	—	PM	PM
Saket 3	Dwarf	Early	—	PM	R	—	PR	PM	PM	PM
Saket 4	Dwarf	Early	R	PR	R	PM	PM	—	PM	PM
Sarjoo 52	Dwarf	Medium	PR	PR	R	PM	PM	—	PM	—
Sattari	Dwarf	Early	PM	—	—	PM	—	—	—	PM
Manhar	Dwarf	Medium	PM	PM	—	PM	PM	PM	—	PM
Sita	Dwarf	Medium	—	PM	—	PM	PR	—	—	—
Madhuri	Dwarf	Early	PM	PM	PR	PM	—	PM	PM	PM
Jaya	Dwarf	Medium	—	PM	—	PM	—	PM	PM	—
Satha 34-36	Tall	Early	R	—	R	PM	—	PM	PM	—
China 4	Tall	Early	PR	PR	PM	PM	—	—	—	—
Boro Gazipur	Tall	Early	—	PM	—	PM	PM	—	—	—
Boro Mirzapur	Tall	Early	—	PM	PM	PM	PM	—	—	PM
Jhona 349	Tall	Early	—	—	PM	—	PM	—	—	—
Cauvery	Dwarf	Early	PM	PR	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Govind	Dwarf	Early	—	PR	PR	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM
Mahsuri	Tall	Late	—	PR	PM	—	PR	—	PM	PM
T100	Tall	Late	PR	—	PR	—	PR	—	—	—
N22	Tall	Early	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM

*R = restorer, PR = partial restorer, PM = partial maintainer.

(WS). Based on spikelet fertility of F₁s, the rice varieties were categorized as effective restorers (80-100% spikelet fertility), partial restorers (21-79% spikelet fertility), partial maintainers (2-20% spikelet fertility), and maintainers (0-1% spikelet fertility).

Narendra 118, Saket 4, and Satha 34-36 were identified as restorers for V20 A and IR54752 A, and IR24 for IR46830 A (Table 2). No varieties were identified as restorers for ES18 A, Madhu A, Pragathi A, Pushpa A, and Mangla A, and no varieties were identi-

fied as effective maintainers for any CMS lines in this study. Results indicate that CMS source wild abortive was genetically diverse from MS577. ■

Genotypic differences in embryogenic callus formation and plant regeneration in indica rice

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Fifteen indica varieties were used for determining response to embryogenic callus induction and plant regeneration (see table). Embryos were separated from mature, dehusked seeds that had been soaked in sterile distilled water for 24 h at 28 °C. Embryos were cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with 3% sucrose and 0.8% agar adjusted

to pH 5.8 and supplemented with 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter.

We observed variations in culture responses among genotypes. Calli formed at the scutellar surface after 1 wk of culture. Himalaya 1 did not form any calli. Genotypes formed either embryogenic or nonembryogenic calli or both types. Embryogenic calli were compact, nodular, loosely globular, shiny, dry in appearance, and yellow to cream in color. Nonembryogenic calli were friable in appearance, white to brown in color, and occasionally developed roots.

On the basis of embryogenic callus formation, Chambal, CH1039, HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B, Himdhan,

HPU5101, HPU2202, and IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2 were selected for regeneration (see table). Four-week-old calli of these genotypes were maintained on MS medium supplemented with 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter. For plant regeneration, calli (about 1.15 g from each callus) from the second subculture were plated onto MS medium supplemented with three levels of BAP (0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/liter) and NAA (0.05, 0.1, and 0.5 mg/liter) in various combinations.

We observed that calli did not regenerate at 0.5 mg BAP/liter and 0.05 mg NAA/liter. At the higher level BAP and NAA combination, a high frequency of regeneration was observed in Chambal, CH1039, and Himdhan